

Introduction

In the middle of 19th century, a Norwegian mathematician, named by Sophus Lie, proposed a powerful method to extract symmetries and invariants of differential equations¹.

This method can be described by the following flowchart:

If a differential equation presents symmetries it is necessary that the Lie Condition² be satisfied:

$$(\chi + \mathcal{U}'')\mathcal{F} = 0$$

where $\chi = \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u}$ is the symmetry generator and $\mathcal{U}'' = \beta^{(1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial u'} + \beta^{(2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial u''}$ is the operator, ξ and η are the infinitesimal functions of symmetry and $\beta^{(1)}$ and $\beta^{(2)}$ the extensions of the first and second order derivatives, respectively.

Scheme of Noether Theorem

The invariant \mathcal{A} , or physical quantity conserved under the symmetry transformation, calculated from the Noether Theorem is given by:

$$\mathcal{A} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{u}} (u\xi - \eta) - \mathcal{L}\xi \Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx}\mathcal{A} = 0$$

where \dot{u} is the derivative of u related to the time and \mathcal{L} is the lagrangian of the system.

Example Application

The equation of the elastic line for the analysis section $l < x < 2l$ is:

$$EI \frac{d^2}{dx^2} u(x) - V_A x - V_B (x - l) + qx^2 - \frac{qx^3}{12l} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $u(x)$ is the deflection, EI is the flexural stiffness and V_A and V_B are the reactions.

The fourth and seventh symmetry generators are given by the expressions:

$$\chi_4 = 6EI \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + x^2 [24l(V_A + V_B) + q(x^2 - 16lx)] \frac{\partial}{\partial u} \quad (2)$$

$$\chi_7 = 60x^2 EI l \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + x [-30l(V_B l x^2 + 2EIu) + 20lx^3(V_A + V_B) + qx^4(x - 15l)] \frac{\partial}{\partial u} \quad (3)$$

From Noether's Theorem and with χ_4 we have the symmetry information associated to the invariant \mathcal{A}_4 when $x = 2l$:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \mathcal{A}_4 = 0 \Rightarrow 10q\ell^2 - 6V_A\ell - 3V_B\ell = 0$$

which corresponds to the sum of bending moments at the point C.

With the seventh symmetry generator, new coordinates that facilitate the integration can be obtained:

$$x_7 = \frac{1}{240EI\ell x} [qx^4(20l - x) - 40lx^3(V_A + V_B) + 120l(V_B l x^2 + 2EIu)]; \quad u_7(x_7) = -\frac{1}{60EI\ell x}$$

Thus, the differential equation in the new variables and their solution are given by:

$$\frac{d^2}{dx_7^2} u_7(x_7) = 0 \Rightarrow u_7(x_7) = C_1 x_7 + C_2 \quad (4)$$

where C_1 e C_2 are constants of integration.

By substituting the expressions for x_7 and u_7 in the calculated solution, we have the solution of the equation of elastic line in the original coordinates:

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{240EI\ell} \left[qx^4(x - 20l) + 40x\ell^3(V_A + V_B) - 120V_B x^2\ell^2 - \frac{240EI\ell x C_2 + 4}{C_1} \right] \quad (5)$$

Final Remarks

- The invariant \mathcal{A}_4 , related to the fourth symmetry operation, is associated to the sum of bending moments at the point C.
- The generator χ_7 provides new variables through canonical transformations facilitating the solution.
- Possibility of proposing a new method in the form of a theorem for the calculation of deflection, support reactions and strain energy in hyperstatic beams involving Lie Symmetries.

References

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Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the financial support provided by CNPq - Grant number 404463/2016-9 and to FAPESP - Grant number 2016/22473-6.